

Momentum Versus Kinetic Energy/Energy in Kinematics

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Momentum and kinetic energy are present in Newtonian mechanics as fundamental ideas. Here, we try to consider how they arise in a practical sense. We consider momentum as being linked with a force interaction which occurs at specific x, t in a tiny dt , and is associated with a specific interaction arrangement in space, i.e. the force vector. We note that given the specific orientation, momentum is a vector (without knowing its explicit functional form) and it depends on the particular co-ordinate system used. One would expect $dp/dt = F$ without any of these being formally defined except that dt is tiny time interval.

If on the other hand, there is a starting and ending point in space with many interaction points in between (in fact so many that each (x, y, z) point is seen as an interaction point), then there is a different p_x, p_y, p_z at each point as well as an initial p_{x0}, p_{y0}, p_{z0} and p_{xf}, p_{yf}, p_{zf} (0 =initial, f =final). Given that one is not dealing with a specific interaction at t which takes dt , one is interested in a path in space between the two points with continuous interaction. In such a case, one has $F(x, y, z)$ instead of $F(t)$ so $dp = F dt$ becomes $v \cdot dp = F \cdot dr$. If the integral is path independent, i.e. $F = -\text{grad } V$, then one may evaluate a scalar $V(x, y, z \text{ final}) - V(x, y, z \text{ initial})$ and there should exist a rotationally invariant function associated with the particle which may also be evaluated at the endpoints. If p is p proportional to v as an example, then a rotational scalar is constant $v \cdot v$. Thus, one has both the vector p for specific point interactions and the scalar E for path independent continuous interactions, and the two are related due to the notion of vector and rotational scalar.

In Newtonian mechanics, one may note that giving a particle a hit (force) in a certain direction creates a velocity vector in that direction. Now momentum (which is of yet not defined) is also a vector. One might guess that it is linked to the vector v , but if that is the case, one needs a full functional form for momentum. (Incidentally, if momentum were proportional to v vector, then a rotational invariant is $v \cdot v$ and measure which is independent of a the co-ordinate system should be a function of $v \cdot v$.)

In order to find a full expression for momentum and even the co-ordinate system independent scalar, one may consider viewing a particle from frames moving at different speeds, i.e. special relativity. A Lorentz transformation changes the vector r and number t , but if one has a rest mass m_0 (a number), then in a moving frame it has a velocity. If one applies a transformation for r, t to 0 , one may create an explicit vector p and number E by assuming that there is an invariant modulus, i.e. a link between m_0 and p, E . This necessarily involves a $(1, -1)$ metric instead of the usual $(1, 1)$ for physical reasons. Given p and E , these are not simply math creations as the fact that a particle is seen as moving means that it was given a hit.

In the Newtonian world, this may be described by $dp_1/dt = \text{force}$. Here p_1 is the Newtonian momentum (which might be different from the special relativity one), dt is tiny and implies a specific interaction at t and a position in space (together with its spatial geometrical force situation). One also wishes to have a co-ordinate independent scalar linked with p_1 .

Given the explicit forms for $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$, one may see that in the $v/c \ll 1$ limit, $p = m_0 v$ and $E = m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 v \cdot v$. Thus, if $p = p_1$, then $.5 m_0 v \cdot v$ is the

co-ordinate invariant (rotational invariant one seeks, as m_0 is already rotational invariant and does not change form during the continuous interactions from the initial 0 point to the final f one.

A Single Interaction Versus a Continuous Set of Interactions

If one considers a push a pull (i.e. a force). it may be in any direction relative to a given co-ordinate system and leads to a velocity vector in the same direction. It seems that such a reaction occurs at a given point in space at time t , takes a tiny dt and depends on the spatial geometry of the force. As a result, one may consider two outcomes for the particle, an already mentioned velocity vector and a new unknown vector p linked to the interaction. One might speculate that p is proportional to v , but even so the exact functional form of p is unknown. One may write:

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \quad ((1))$$

Here p is the unknown vector and dt is considered to be a tiny instant as this represents a single interaction and even Force is not precisely defined. Examples include a particle striking a piece of glass and breaking it, striking a mirror or two body interactions at a point with short range forces.

Alternatively, one may consider a particle undergoing one interaction after another. In fact, one might consider continuous interactions at each x,y,z . This could be linked to long range forces or many short range interactions. In such a case, one has:

$$\text{An initial momentum } p_{x0}, p_{y0}, p_{z0} \text{ and a final momentum } p_{xf}, p_{yf}, p_{zf} \quad ((2))$$

We noted that p as a vector is particularly useful for a single interaction, but if there are many interactions, one might ask how practical $dp/dt = F$ is. In particular, one would then think of $F(x,y,z)$ and not $F(t)$ and so:

$$dp = \text{Force } dt \rightarrow v \cdot dp = \text{Force} \cdot v \cdot dt = \text{Force} \cdot dr \quad ((3))$$

((3)) shows that one may consider a path in space and obtain a scalar quantity linked to the overall interaction. If p were proportional to the vector v , then

$$v \cdot v \quad ((4a))$$

would be a rotationally invariant quantity.

Path Invariance

Given the scalar integral in ((3)) over dr , one may ask whether the specific path taken matters. If it does not, then one only needs information about the initial point and the final point and so a

function that is rotationally invariant, i.e. a scalar (in terms of rotation) suffices. For path independent situations, one has (as is well known)

$$F = -\text{grad } V, \text{ where } V \text{ is a potential ((4b))}$$

If F is experimentally known in terms of $F(x,y,z)$, then $V(x,y,z)$ is also known and may be compared with the change in constant $v \cdot v$ (if in fact the scalar quantity is proportional to $v \cdot v$). In other words, one would not calculate $F(t) dt$ over time to find Δp for the continuous case because it is $F(x,y,z)$ which is known. One would then need a rotationally invariant function linked to the particle which may also be evaluated at the start and end points. If p is proportional to v , then $v \cdot v$ would be an example of such a rotational invariant, but ultimately one must find an exact expression for p and E (the rotational invariant).

Momentum, Energy and Special Relativity

In the above section, we considered a vector p (possibly proportional to the vector v) and a rotationally invariant scalar (possibly proportional to $v \cdot v$) as describing a single interaction or a continuous one. We, however, did provide formal definitions for these quantities.

If one views a particle from one frame or another such that these frames move at constant relative speed (i.e. special relativity), one may obtain equations showing the transformation of m_0 (rest mass) into E and p . (Here we call E_1 and p_1 the postulated values from the previous section because the two sets might not be equal.)

One may immediately consider a transformation for the vector r and number t because in one dimension, a particle at rest at $x=0$, t is seen as moving by a frame moving at $-v$ to the rest one. If $x=0, t=0$ and $x'=0, t'=0$ for the initial points of both frames, then x' cannot equal x , but one must have:

$$x'/t' = v \quad ((5))$$

If one assumes that x and t both changes (an assumption which will later prove necessary) then one may write:

$$x' = g(v) v t \quad \text{and} \quad t' = g(v) t \quad ((6))$$

At this point, $g(v)$ is unknown. Furthermore, one should really have $g(v/c)$ where c is a constant speed which does not depend on the frame and so represents an upper bound on speed. From special relativity this is c , the speed of light in a vacuum.

Given the transformation of the number t and vector r , one may consider that there is a second number in the rest frame, namely m_0 . This will be seen to be moving with v (velocity vector) and so one might consider the transformation of $((6))$ acting $(0, m_0 \cdot \text{constant})$. For $\text{constant} = cc$, this yields:

$$p' = \gamma(v) v m_0 c \quad \text{and} \quad E' = \gamma(v) m_0 c^2 \quad ((7))$$

The transformation ((6)) may be viewed in terms of a 2x2 matrix and one may note that the two frames represent the same physical system. One might argue for an invariant (i.e. a quantity which has the same value in each frame.). Usually, this would be the modulus squared:

$$p' \cdot p' + E'E' \quad ((8))$$

((8)), however, cannot be correct for the following reason. Even though p' and E' above represent math quantities, physically moving an object requires a force and work as seen in the first section. Thus, $p' > 0$ and $E' > m_0 c^2$. This means that one should consider a minus between the two quantities in ((8)). Then:

$$p' \cdot p' c^2 - E'E' = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((9)) \text{ or}$$

$$g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((10))$$

Comparison of p', E' from Special Relativity with Newtonian p, E

In the first section, we considered a momentum p such that $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ together with a rotationally invariant scalar. In the above section, we obtained a vector p' and scalar E' from considerations of frames moving at constant relative speed, but also from the notion that $E' > m_0 c^2$ due to work. Thus, the idea of force and work is present in the special relativistic p', E' . The question is whether it fully matches p, E from the Newtonian case.

If, as an example, one considers $v/c \ll 1$, then:

$$p' = m_0 v \quad \text{and} \quad E' = m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 v \cdot v \quad ((11))$$

p' then matches the speculated vector proportional to velocity and $.5 m_0 v \cdot v$ is rotationally invariant, i.e. represents the scalar. Furthermore $m_0 c^2$ is a constant which is rotationally invariant. As a result, the functions from special relativity seem to capture what was sought in the first section.

As a result, it seems that one requires a number (rotationally invariant scalar) to describe continuous interactions in which the path taken does not matter, while the p vector is required for a single interaction at a point in space (or one in which the path taken matters).

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems practical to introduce a vector quantity p (momentum) possibly proportional to v (velocity) to describe a single interaction involving short range forces at a point x at time t . This leads to $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ where p is unknown. If on the other hand one has long

range forces or continuous interaction in space, one should have $F(x,y,z)$ and not think in terms of a change in dt and p . This leads to:

$$dp = F dt \rightarrow v \cdot dp = F \cdot v dt = F \cdot dr$$

If the integral is path invariant, then one should have a scalar quantity which depends only on the start and endpoints for the F integral, i.e. (for $F = -\text{grad } V$, this depends on $V(r \text{ final}) - V(r \text{ initial})$) where V is a scalar function. Similarly, there should be a rotationally invariant function linked to the particle.

We then show that one may find such quantities by using special relativity, i.e. $p = m_0 v$ (vector) / $\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $E = m_0cc/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. In the $v/c \ll 1$ limit, $E = m_0cc + .5m_0 v \cdot v$, where $v \cdot v$ is rotationally invariant.